

Introducing re3data – the Registry of Research Data Repositories

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ABSTRACT

re3data is the global registry for research data repositories [1]. As of September 2021, the service lists over 2700 digital repositories across all scientific disciplines and provides an extensive description of repositories based on a detailed metadata schema, the updated version of which was recently published [2]. The service promotes open science practices and the visibility of science-driven open infrastructures. A variety of funders, publishers, and scientific organizations around the world refer to re3data within their guidelines and policies, recommending the service to researchers looking for appropriate repositories for storage and discovery of research data [3].

The re3data web interface and API function as an important Science Gateway, allowing its end users and other services to access the largest index of research data repositories in the world [4]. Since January 2020, the re3data COREF project receives funding from the German Research Foundation (DFG) to further develop and enhance the registry service [5].

The planned presentation will introduce the re3data service and give an overview of the ongoing project work, including a short introduction to the recently published “Conceptual Model for User Stories” for re3data [6]. The editorial process for the inclusion of repositories in re3data will be explained and participants will learn how to submit new entries and suggest

changes. Participants will also learn how to retrieve information and metadata from re3data.

Keywords — Research Data Repositories, Repository Registry, Index, re3data COREF project

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